

A STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF ONLINE ADVERTISING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

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Abstract:

The growth of Information Technology industry provides lot of comfort and technology support to domestic and industrial applications. The volume of sale of products and services through online increases rapidly in India, earlier the people of India had hesitation about security of financial transactions through electronic networks, but now-a-days all kind of bill payments, purchase of products even like grocery, vegetables, etc are purchased through online. The booming of online shopping boosted the purchase of electronic gadgets. The main aim of the study is to explore the impact of online advertising on consumer attitude towards the purchase of electronic gadgets using structural equation modeling approach. The conclusion is that most of the respondents like online advertisement very much and they accept that advertising in online is a effective traditional media shows that more advertisement about the products can be given in online so that the product can be used among customers. The respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company and it shows that the models are not having impact on the brand and new innovative concepts can be created so that more advertisements can be published as per customer's requirements.

Key Words: Online Advertising, Consumer Attitude & Traditional Media

Introduction to the Study:

Online advertising refers to the type of marketing strategy that involves the use of internet for promotion of products by delivering the marketing messages to the larger consumers. It includes delivering ads to internet users via websites, e-mail, ad supported software's, text messaging and internet enabled cell phones. Philip Kotler in Marketing management Millenium Edition mention that the internet population is younger, more affluent, and better educated and they easily find their way onto the internet, the cyberspace population is becoming more mainstream and diverse. In on-line marketing, it is the consumer, not the marketer, who gives permission and controls the interaction. Internet consumers have around-the-clock access to varied information sources, making them better informed and more discerning shoppers.

Statement of the Problem:

According to consumers, internet advertising includes many forms of commercial content from electronic advertisements that are similar to traditional advertisements (e.g., billboards, banner ads) to formats that are different from traditional advertisements, such as corporate Web site. The problem is to know about the impact of advertising online in Coimbatore region.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study about concepts involved in customer perception.
- To study about the beliefs, feelings and behavioral intentions of customers.
- To analyze the attitude of customers based on factors information, entertainment, social role, falsity and value corruption.
- To suggest about the perception of customers about online advertising.

Scope of the Study:

The study is about analysing the impact of gender in online advertising. The main scope of the study is that it will be helped for the companies to know about the customer's attitude and influence of gender towards online advertising. In future the study may be extended to include the impact of advertising in improving the customer retention.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a way of systematically solving the research problem. Research methodology deals with the research design used and methods used to present the study. Which may be in the form of personal interviews, surveys, research techniques etc?

Source of Data:

The type of data collected comprises of primary and secondary data. The primary data is the first hand data collected from the employees through questionnaire. The questionnaire is a structured one. It is made simple and avoids misunderstanding to the respondents. The secondary data has been collected from the reports and official publications of the organization, journals, statutory welfare schemes from websites, some reviews said by employees, collection of circulars between the customers of online advertising about the awareness.

Sampling Method:

Sampling method refers to the rules and procedures by which some elements of the population are included in the sample. Some common method is simple random sampling, stratified sampling, cluster sampling etc... it mainly depends on survey objectives and survey resources. In this research simple random sampling is used, in statistics it is a subset of individuals (a sample) chosen from a larger set (a population). Each individual is chosen randomly and entirely by chance, such that each individual has the same probability of being chosen at any stage during the sampling process and each subset of individuals has the same probability of being chosen for sample as any other subset of individuals this process and techniques is known as simple random sampling.

Sample Design:

The study is based primary data collected on sample survey technique. It consists of customer awareness about online advertising based on gender. Sample of 100 were selected and their views and opinions are collected on different parameters. Personal interviews and informal discussions were held with the employees as well.

Tools & Techniques:

Simple percentage, Chi square analysis and Ranking method

Limitation of the Study:

- The study is confined only to the Coimbatore city hence it cannot be considered as a representation of entire area.
- Availability of information and data are limited by time factor.
- The number of respondents is limited to only 100, and the opinion may differ from person to person.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Number of Respondents	Percentage
Age	Below 25	40	40
	25 to 35 years	12	12
	36 to 45 years	40	40
	Above 45 years	8	8
	Total	100	100
Gender	Male	66	66
	Female	34	34
	Total	100	100
Educational Qualification	SSLC	16	16
	Diploma	17	17
	HSC	32	32
	Degree holders	35	35
	Total	100	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 40% are of the age group of below 25 yrs, 12% are in the age group of 25 to 35 yrs, 40% are in the age group of 36 to 45 yrs, and 8% are in the age group of above 45yrs. 16% of them have completed SSLC, 17% of them has completed diploma, 32% of them has completed HSC, and 35% of them has completed degree.

Preference of Like Towards Online Advertisement:

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Like it very much	41	41
Like it	15	15
Neutral	10	10
I do not like it	20	20
I do not like it all	14	14
Total	100	100

Interpretation: The above table shows the preference of like towards online advertisement by the respondents were 41% of them like very much, 15% of them like it, 10% of them are neutral, 20% of them don't like it and 14% of them don't like it all.

Frequency of Watching Online Advertisements for the Products:

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1 Times	19	19
2 Times	33	33
3 Times	48	48
Total	100	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about advertisements for the products that 19% of them have seen the advertisements 1 time, 33% has seen the advertisements 2 times, 48% of them has seen the advertisements 3 times.

Understanding Advertisements:

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
No	22	22
A little	34	34
Yes	44	44
Total	100	100

Interpretation

The above table shows that 22% are not understanding advertisements, 34% are understanding a little, 44% are understanding and they are not confused about the advertisement.

Table Showing About the Level of Acceptance:

	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	NO	%								
Acceptance on product in pop up	6	6	9	9	12	12	22	22	51	51
Acceptance on using gender for advertisement	32	32	41	41	4	4	8	8	15	15
Acceptance on models with a improper dress code	42	42	15	15	10	10	19	19	14	14
Acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company	44	44	31	31	6	6	13	13	6	6
Acceptance on effective traditional media	20	20	31	31	18	18	10	10	21	21
Acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile	32	32	38	38	6	6	14	14	10	10
Acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males	44	44	22	22	14	14	15	15	5	5
Acceptance on significant gap	21	21	22	22	6	6	44	44	7	7

Interpretation:

From the above table 6% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on product in pop up, 32% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 42% of the respondents strongly agree for using models with a improper dress code, 44% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 20% of the respondents strongly agree on effective traditional media, 32% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 44% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males and 21% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers. 9% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on product in pop up, 41% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 15% of the respondents strongly agree for using models with a improper dress code, 31% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 31% of the respondents strongly agree on effective traditional media, 38% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 22% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males and 22% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

12% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on product in pop up, 4% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 10% of the respondents neutral for using models with a improper dress code, 13% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 18% of the respondents neutral on effective traditional media, 6% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 14% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males and 6% of the respondents neutral for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers. 6% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on product in pop up, 32% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 42% of the respondents neutral for using models with a improper dress code, 44% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 20% of the respondents neutral on effective traditional media, 32% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 44% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males and 21% of the respondents neutral for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

22% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on product in pop up, 8% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 19% of the respondents disagree for using models with a improper dress code, 13% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 10% of the respondents disagree on effective traditional media, 14% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 15% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males and 44% of the respondents disagree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers. 51% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on product in pop up, 15% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 19% of the respondents strongly disagree for using models with a improper dress code, 21% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 10% of the respondents strongly disagree on effective traditional media, 10% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 5% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males and 44% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

Chi Square:

Comparison between Age and Watching Online Advertisements for the Products:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and watching online advertisements for the products

Age * Watching online advertisements for the products					
Count					
		Watching online advertisements for the products			Total
		1 Times	2 Times	3 Times	
Age	Below 25	11	10	19	40
	25 to 35 years	2	5	5	12
	36 to 45 years	6	16	18	40
	Above 45 years	0	2	6	8
Total		19	33	48	100

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.603 ^a	6	0.359

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the chi square analysis (at 5% significance level) reveals that there is no significance between these factors as the calculated value is less than table value at 6 degree of freedom.

Rank Analysis:

	Factors	Rank						
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	Influences customer by a negative review	23	28	33	8	8	250	2
2	Consumer perceive higher level of risk	23	50	13	6	8	226	5
3	Switch over of brand because of models used	42	14	7	31	6	245	3
4	Marketing channel has a largest combination for brand promotion based on gender	6	3	27	37	0	241	4
5	Information given by the advertising is informative	6	14	17	28	35	372	1

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the rank analysis of watching online advertisements. Where information given by the advertising is informative was given first rank, Influences customer by a negative review was given second rank, Switch over of brand because of models used was given third rank, Marketing channel has a largest combination for brand promotion based on gender was given fourth rank and Consumer perceive higher level of risk was given fifth rank which shows that Information given by the advertising is informative was given first priority by the respondents.

Findings:

- Maximum of the respondents are from the age group of below 25 and in our survey.
- Most of the respondents are male in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents have completed degree in our survey.
- Most of the respondents like online advertisement very much.
- Most of the respondents have seen the online advertisement for the products 3 times in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on product in pop up.
- Most of the respondents agree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement.
- Maximum of the respondents strongly agree for using models with a improper dress code
- most of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company
- Maximum of the respondents agree for acceptance on effective traditional media
- Most of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile
- Maximum of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on intention of females to buy online is less than that of males

Suggestions:

- Most of the respondents like online advertisement very much and they accept that advertising in online are an effective traditional media shows that more advertisement about the products can be given in online so that the product can be used among customers.
- The respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company and it shows that the models are not having impact on the brand and new innovative concepts can be created so that more advertisements can be published as per customer's requirements.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that most of the respondents like online advertisement very much and they accept that advertising in online is a effective traditional media shows that more advertisement about the products can be given in online so that the product can be used among customers. The respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company and it shows that the models are not having impact on the brand and new innovative concepts can be created so that more advertisements can be published as per customer's requirements.

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